

NOSTRUM

Optimizing Floating Offshore Wind Turbines For Use In The Mediterranean Sea

M3 - M5

*REPORT - SELECTION, OPTIMIZATION,
SET-UP AND SIMULATION OF A
BASELINE TURBINE MODEL*

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1. Introduction and Scope

The scope of this activity is twofold: first, to define initial configurations for the advanced design optimization procedure planned for WP4-M5; second, to establish reference aerodynamic conditions for the blades and loading conditions for the tower top and base. These configurations will provide a starting point for the sizing and testing of floating platform models (WP2-M3), defining optimal control strategies (WP3-M4), and optimizing blade aerodynamic airfoils for low wind conditions (WP4-M5).

As a starting point, the virtual model of the IEA 15 MW (1) is implemented to perform multi-body aero-servo-elastic simulations of the turbine working in the reference site conditions defined in WP1. The simulations are carried on using the wind turbine engineering code OpenFast (2).

In WP1 [M1_D1] the project consortium identified that a possible wind turbine design class to use in the definition of the new reference FOWT for the Mediterranean case is the Class III.

The reference IEA 15 MW turbine is a Class II turbine designed for higher winds therefore, its shape and radius may not be optimal for energy extraction on the new case of application. Therefore, in this preliminary work we re-design the rotor blades and try three possible radial extension, verifying later that the new design have not significant impact on the supporting structures. This will provide a a) parametric study to determine the effect of increasing the energy capture area in terms of loads b) define a more suitable baseline rotor model for future advanced optimization of floater and turbine.

The aerodynamic design of wind turbine blades is crucial for optimizing energy capture, particularly for floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) in the Mediterranean Sea, where wind speeds tend to be moderate and operational challenges are heightened by deep-water conditions. This report summarizes the efforts made to design and optimize a new rotor blade geometry using a multi-fidelity analysis framework (3), (4), (5). The methodology, which integrates surrogate models and genetic algorithms (GAs), focuses on achieving efficient aerodynamic optimization specifically tailored to Mediterranean wind conditions.

The document outlines the overall framework developed for blade optimization, the results obtained, and the next steps to be taken in this project. A key aspect of this work is the design case of the IEA 15MW reference turbine, starting from the DTU FFA-W3 series. The primary focus of this task is to optimize the blade geometry, including the airfoil shape, chord, and twist distributions, in order to maximize Annual Energy Production (AEP). Once the initial objective is addressed, the scope is expanded to incorporate additional design criteria, allowing for a more comprehensive optimization

The study then focuses on the definition and setup of a virtual model for the dynamic simulation of the offshore reference wind turbine set on a baseline design of possible semi-submersible floating platform. In this phase we start from the definition of the UMaine VolturUS-S semi-submersible floating platform to setup the model (6). The analysis aims to prepare all the folders and files required for the simulation of the FOWT, and verify the coupled dynamics of the turbine-platform system, with emphasis on the interactions between aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, and structural effects. The structural flexibility of the turbine's blades and tower is explicitly considered in this case to ensure an accurate representation of the system's behaviour under offshore environmental conditions.

In addition, a parametric study is conducted to investigate the impact of rotor radius variations on system performance. Configurations with the baseline rotor radius, as well as increases of 5% and

10%, are examined to evaluate the trade-offs between enhanced energy capture and the resulting dynamic loads on the floating platform.

2. Rotor blades design

This section outlines the aerodynamic optimization of wind turbine blades tailored for offshore applications in the Mediterranean Sea. The goal is to enhance energy capture by adjusting key geometric parameters of the blade, such as chord length and twist distribution. These efforts are aimed at balancing aerodynamic efficiency with structural constraints under the moderate wind conditions typical of the target region.

2.2 Blade cord and twist optimization method

The aerodynamic optimization of the wind turbine blade was conducted using a multi-fidelity framework integrating surrogate models and genetic algorithms (GAs). The primary goal was to maximize the turbine's Annual Energy Production (AEP) by refining the twist and chord distributions along the blade span. This method enabled efficient exploration of complex design spaces while balancing computational cost and accuracy. Given the moderate wind speeds prevalent in Mediterranean conditions, the optimization process emphasized achieving high efficiency at low-to-moderate wind velocities. This focus influenced both the cost function and the constraints applied during the optimization.

The optimization process begins by selecting the primary objective, which is to maximize AEP over a range of wind velocities. The cost function is defined as:

$$AEP_{12}(x) = \Delta T \int_{V_1}^{V_2} P(V, x) f_V(V) dV$$

Where $P(V, x)$ is the aerodynamic power of the rotor at wind speed V , $f_V(V)$ is the probability density function of the wind speed at the target site, x denotes the design variables, specifically the twist and chord distributions and ΔT represents the evaluation period (one year). The AEP function was integrated over a wind speed from $V_1 = 4 \text{ m/s}$ to $V_2 = 9 \text{ m/s}$, reflecting the moderate wind conditions typical of Mediterranean Sea sites.

The second step is the definition of the blade geometry parametrization. According to recent literature (4), (7), the blade shape should be defined with a controlled number of parameters to avoid excessively large variable space, which could lead to numerous saddle points or require an impractical number of cost function evaluations during the optimization procedure.

The blade geometry was parametrized using a cubic B-spline for the twist distribution, controlled by five key points along the span, while the chord distribution was governed by a single control point located at mid-span ($r/R = 0.59$), four root and five tip fixed control points. The airfoil shapes and their corresponding thickness-to-chord ratios were predefined based on aerodynamic efficiency and were held constant throughout the optimization process to focus the study on the aerodynamic improvements driven by twist and chord variations. Constraints were applied to both the twist and chord distributions to avoid unfeasible geometries and ensure that the optimized designs met structural and aerodynamic performance requirements. Figure 1 shows the spline interpolation and control points of the ϑ function (Figure 1a) and the c function (Figure 1b).

Figure 1: Design space control points (black markers), spline interpolation (black line) and reference blade values (red dashed line) for the twist and chord distributions along the blade span.

Other constraints applied to the variables are simple in-equality constraints that limit the range of variation to avoid unfeasible design geometries.

The optimization is conducted using a genetic algorithm (GA) to explore the design space and optimize the blade geometry. Unlike traditional gradient-based methods, which may struggle with the non-linearities present in the design space, the GA is capable of avoiding local minima and identifying globally optimal solutions.

The objective function in this initial phase of the optimization is to maximize AEP (Annual Energy Production), with subsequent phases allowing the introduction of additional objectives (such as costs, weight, or lifespan) and constraints (such as structural integrity and fatigue resistance).

The GA is initialized with a population of 200 potential solutions, each representing a different configuration of twist and chord control points. Through selection, crossover, and mutation operations, the algorithm evolves over successive generations to improve the design's fitness. The process continues until the optimal solution is found or the improvement in AEP falls below a predefined threshold of 1%.

Given the high computational cost of running full aerodynamic simulations repeatedly, the direct evaluation of the cost function is replaced with a Stochastic Radial-basis Functions (SRBF) Surrogate Model (8). The approach aims to efficiently approximate complex objective functions $f(x)$ such as AEP_{12} in Eq. 1, through a reduced-order model based on regression functions that are defined and refined using a limited number of full-order model (FOR) computations.

The metamodel is constructed using stochastic Radial Basis Functions (SRBFs):

$$f(y, \tau) = \sum_{j=1}^K w_j \|y - c_j\|^\tau$$

Where the centers c_j are optimized via clustering and coefficients w_j are determined through least squares regression, $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm, K number of RBFs and τ is the Kernel parameter considered $\tau \sim unif[1,3]$. This allows the surrogate model to capture variability in design parameters and accurately interpolate the simulation data. The adaptive sampling strategy is employed to iteratively refine the surrogate model by focusing on regions with the highest uncertainty. Using this approach, new training points are automatically added where the model exhibits the greatest uncertainty, ensuring that the surrogate model improves its accuracy where it is most needed, thus avoiding unnecessary computations of the FOR.

In parallel with this strategy, the airfoil polars are dynamically adjusted to reflect changes in the chord length during optimization. Since the thickness is fixed, maintaining a consistent thickness-to-chord ratio (t/c) is crucial for accurate aerodynamic predictions. This is achieved by selecting or interpolating airfoil polars from the IEA-15-240-RWT reference database.

Once the surrogate model is trained and validated, it is integrated into the GA framework. The optimization process refines the aerodynamic performance by iteratively adjusting twist and chord distributions (see Figure 2). The GA uses the surrogate model to rapidly evaluate different configurations, ensuring that the optimization converges quickly on the best possible solution.

The optimization is performed in MATLAB R2024a, with a population size of 200, a mutation rate of 0.01, and a crossover fraction of 0.8. By minimizing direct simulation costs, the surrogate model accelerates the GA's convergence, allowing for significant performance improvements in a fraction of the time required for full simulations.

Figure 2: Flowchart depicting the process of a genetic algorithm, including population initialization, fitness evaluation, selection, crossover, mutation, and termination, iterating until an optimal or satisfactory solution is found.

2.3 Test cases

The IEA-15-240-RWT (1) served as the test case, a 15MW horizontal-axis wind turbine featuring a 240m rotor diameter, a 150m hub height, and a tip-speed ratio of 9. This turbine model was selected due to its compatibility with the expected size of modern offshore wind turbines for future installations, providing a robust and complete baseline model for examining the impacts of rotor geometry changes and assessing their aerodynamic performance improvements. The new rotor is then optimized for IEC Class III conditions, making it more suitable for the moderate wind speeds typical of the Mediterranean.

To explore how rotor size affected energy capture, three different rotor configurations were tested: the baseline rotor (Design 1), a rotor with a 5% increase in radius (Design 2), and a rotor with a 10% increase in radius (Design 3). Given that the turbine was being designed specifically for Mediterranean wind conditions, wind data was sourced from the ERA5 reanalysis database. This data provided a Weibull probability density function for wind speed distribution at 100m above mean sea level, which was then scaled using a power law to more accurately represent wind conditions at the 150m hub height.

The computation of the blade aerodynamics is performed using *AeroDyn.v15* (9) an open-source dynamic solver based on Blade Element Momentum Theory (BEMT). The blade is divided into 50 blade elements along its span and for each blade element a full AoA range table of aerodynamic coefficients is associated.

As the reference case and initial design, we chose the IEA-15-240-RWT. In this way, we focused only on the aero-dynamics of the blades, assuming the hub, tower, nacelle, electric generator, and other auxiliary structures remain un-altered. The idea is to replace the original rotor and revamp the machine with a newly optimized rotor design tailored to the target wind class. The hub height of the turbine is 150 meters, with a hub radius of 3.97 meters, and the optimal tip-speed ratio is set to 9. The shaft tilt and precone angles are set to -6° and -4° , respectively, as in the reference design.

To investigate the relationship between rotor size and energy capture, a parametric study also explores variable rotor radii, evaluating designs with 5% and 10% larger rotor diameters. The scaling begins at a span point where the thickness-to-chord ratio reaches 21%, with the scaling factor (SF) defined as:

$$SF = \alpha \cdot \frac{R}{h} + 1$$

where α represents the percentage increase needed in rotor diameter, R is the rotor radius and h is the blade section length being scaled.

In this way, there is a smooth extension of the blade radius without any change in the aerodynamic profile of the blade in the root area, where there is less energy extraction.

As outlined in Sec. 2.2, the design space vector is defined by six control points: five for the twist distribution along the span and one for the chord distribution, located at $r/R = 0.59$.

The constraints applied to the design space are as follows:

1. The root and tip control points of the chord distribution are fixed to constrain the maximum and minimum chord values;
2. The upper and lower bounds for the design variable x are defined as:

$[0.19, -3.29, -4.62, -5.97, -4.24, 2.7] < x < [14.19, 8.76, 5.49, 2.20, 1.76, 4.7]$;

3. The maximum cross-sectional thickness is fixed and kept equal to the reference case.

Figure 3: Thickness distribution along the blade span for the three test cases: Design 1 (R), Design 2 (+5 %R) and Design 3 (+10 %R).

After applying these modifications, the updated blade geometry is re-evaluated using the surrogate model to assess the effects of the variable radius on overall aerodynamic performance and AEP.

To reduce computational costs, a surrogate model based on Radial Basis Functions (RBF) is used to approximate the AEP function across the design space. The model is trained using data generated from aerodynamic simulations performed using the AeroDyn.v15 module. The *AeroDyn.v15* tool calculates power at three different uniform wind speeds in the range $V1 = 4 \text{ m/s}$ to $V2 = 9 \text{ m/s}$, which is then used to generate the power curve for each blade design. The power curve is applied to compute the AEP, as outlined in the cost function. To further enhance the accuracy of the surrogate model, an adaptive sampling strategy is implemented. This strategy identifies regions in the design space where the model's predictions are less accurate and adds new training points in those areas. Initially, a uniform grid of design configurations is generated based on the upper and lower bounds for twist and chord control points, ensuring an evenly distributed exploration of the design space. This process continues with increased grid resolution until either a maximum number of iterations is reached or a defined tolerance—three orders of magnitude smaller than the computed AEP—is achieved.

2.4 Surrogate models validation

The accuracy of the surrogate model was validated by comparing its predictions to results obtained from aerodynamic simulations conducted using the AeroDyn.v15 module. This validation process ensured that the surrogate model reliably captured the aerodynamic characteristics of each design configuration.

Validation tests were conducted for all four surrogate models defined in the study: the AEP_{12} function for a rotor with the same radius as the reference blade under IEC Class II and III wind conditions, and for rotors with 5% and 10% radius increases under IEC Class III conditions. The test involved fixing 5 of the 6 design parameters and varying the remaining parameter from its lower to upper bounds. For each combination (which generally falls outside the training grid point set), AEP_{12} was computed first through the surrogate model and then with the AeroDyn.v15 module. The results of the tests are shown in Figure 4 (Design 1 - IEC Class II), Figure 5 (Design 1 - IEC Class III), Figure 6 (Design 2 - IEC Class III), and Figure 7 (Design 3 - IEC Class III).

The surrogate model consistently demonstrated high accuracy in predicting the cost function values, with results closely matching those from AeroDyn.v15 simulations.

Figure 4: Validation of the surrogate model (Design 1, IEC Class II). Continuous lines: surrogate model prediction, dashed lines: AeroDyn.v15 based computation.

Figure 5: Validation of the surrogate model (Design 1, IEC Class III). Continuous lines: surrogate model prediction, dashed lines: AeroDyn.v15 based computation.

Figure 6: Validation of the surrogate model (Design 2, IEC Class III). Continuous lines: surrogate model prediction, dashed lines: AeroDyn.v15 based computation

Figure 7: Validation of the surrogate model (Design 3, IEC Class III). Continuous lines: surrogate model prediction, dashed lines: AeroDyn.v15 based computation

For the Design 1 (R) configuration under IEC Class II conditions, the surrogate model achieved a close match with the AeroDyn-generated AEP values, with a discrepancy of less than 2 %, confirming the reliability of the model in capturing the essential aerodynamic characteristics under higher wind speeds. Similarly, for the IEC Class III conditions, the surrogate model maintained the same level of

accuracy, with deviations from the aerodynamic simulation results also being under 2 % for all rotor radius cases.

A minimal discrepancy was observed for the case of Design 2 when varying the twist angle of the high-midspan control point. Figures 4 through 7 provide a graphical comparison between the surrogate model predictions and the AeroDyn.v15 results. In these figures, continuous lines represent the surrogate model's predictions, while dashed lines illustrate the *AeroDyn*-based computations.

2.5 Rotor aerodynamic tests

This section presents the numerical results from the optimization process, highlighting the impact of variations in twist and chord distributions along the blade span. The analysis utilized the surrogate model based on the radial basis function (RBF) method and the genetic algorithm framework described earlier. The primary objective is to evaluate the aerodynamic performance improvements in terms of annual energy production (AEP) across different design configurations. The results highlight the effectiveness of the optimization strategy, with particular attention given to the modifications in blade geometry and their contribution to enhanced aerodynamic efficiency.

Figure 8 shows the outcome from the optimization algorithm. The GA-driven optimization process successfully improved the aerodynamic performance of the rotor in all three configurations. For Design 1, the baseline rotor with optimized geometry achieved a slight increase in AEP, rising from 2.015 GWh to 2.021 GWh. The performance gains were more substantial for the larger rotors: Design 2, which had a 5% larger radius, achieved an AEP of 2.23 GWh, and Design 3, with a 10% larger radius, reached 2.43 GWh. These results, summarized in Table 1, underscore the benefits of increasing rotor size to capture more energy, especially under the moderate wind conditions characteristic of the Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 8: Optimized twist and chord distribution for Design 1, 2 and 3 wind turbine. The curves represent the optimized distributions obtained from the genetic algorithm.

Table 1: Comparison of aerodynamic performance coefficients (C_p) and annual energy production (AEP) for the reference and optimized rotor design. Results show incremental improvements in AEP with increasing rotor size, despite minor variations in C_p .

	C_p	AEP
Reference	0,487	2.015(GWh)
Design 1 (R)	0,489	2.021(GWh)
Design 2 (+5%R)	0,488	2.22 (GWh)
Design 3 (+10%R)	0,486	2.43 (GWh)

To further investigate the results in terms of aerodynamic behaviour of the blades, Figure 9 illustrates the radial distribution of the angle of attack (AoA) for the different test cases. Across all configurations, the AoA exhibits the typical trend due to changing relative velocities along the span. Differences are noticeable in the midspan region, where 3D effects are less significant, and the 2D-based BEMT design optimizes the aerodynamic load to achieve the best induction and torque. The aerodynamic load of the blade strip depends on the lift, drag, induction, and peripheral velocity, as well as the chord length. Therefore, we observe that Designs 1 and 2, which have larger chord lengths in this area, require smaller angles of attack compared to the reference design and Design 3 to achieve the same local aerodynamic load. Additionally, the constraint of maintaining the same TSR for all designs forces Designs 2 and 3 to operate at lower rotational velocities, requiring larger angles of attack for Design 2 compared to Design 1, and for Design 3 compared to all others.

Figure 9: Angle of attack as a function of radius for the four tests. Reference configuration (dashed black line); Design 1 (solid blue line), Design 2 (solid red line), Design 3 (solid green line).

In addition, the power curves for the reference and optimized configurations were obtained by running OpenFAST.v3.5.1 simulations of the rigid rotor, assuming a constant tip speed ratio in Region 2 (variable speed generator) and constant power in Region 3. The simulation ran for 300 seconds, and the rotor power value was averaged over the last 100 seconds. As expected, increasing the rotor size reduces the nominal power density but also reduces the wind speed at which the rotor reaches nominal power. Therefore, Region 3 is defined by assuming that the pitch control is activated to limit the maximum power to 15 MW. Figure 10 shows the power output as a function of wind speed for the

four different rotor configurations considered. From the power calculation using OpenFAST, the AEP value was calculated for three different wind classes: IEC Class 2, IEC Class 3, IEC Class 4. This results shown that increasing the rotor radius results in an upward shift in the power curve, especially in the rated region, where the larger blades capture more energy. Table 2 summarizes the AEP, capacity factor (CF), and percentage increase in AEP ($\Delta\%$) with respect to the value obtained with the same wind class using the reference IEA 15MW design. As shown, the AEP increases with larger rotor sizes, leading to an increase in CF, highlighting the aerodynamic gains from the optimized blade geometries.

Figure 10: Rotor power curves as a function of wind speed for the four tests. Reference configuration (dashed black line); Design 1 (solid blue line), Design 2 (solid orange line), Design 3 (solid green line).

Table 2: Comparison of Annual Energy Production (AEP) and Capacity Factor (CF) for the different rotor designs and for IEC Wind Classes 2, 3, and 4.

Design	IEC Class 2 AEP (GWh)	IEC Class 2 CF	$\Delta\%$
Reference	67.114	0.511	0
Design 1 (R)	67.211	0.512	0,1
Design 2 (+5%R)	69.831	0.531	4
Design 3 (+10%R)	71.826	0.547	7
	IEC Class 3 AEP (GWh)	IEC Class 3 CF	
Reference	56.591	0.431	0
Design 1 (R)	56.691	0.431	0,2
Design 2 (+5%R)	59.405	0.452	5
Design 3 (+10%R)	61.494	0.468	8,7
	IEC Class 4 AEP (GWh)	IEC Class 4 CF	

Reference	50.672	0.386	0
Design 1 (R)	50.771	0.386	0,2
Design 2 (+5%R)	53.478	0.407	5,5
Design 3 (+10%R)	55.576	0.423	9,7

After confirming the positive impact of the optimization on increasing AEP, the loads acting on the three different designs were analyzed. Figure 11 and Figure 12 illustrate the edgewise and flap-wise moments along the blade span. The percentage increase in the root loads (at $x = 0$) was calculated to assess how the change in rotor radius affected the loads and whether they remain acceptable from a structural standpoint. The results are summarized in Table 3, where it is evident that the flap-wise and edgewise loads experience maximum percentage increases of 22% and 24% for Design 3, respectively, which aligns with the expectation that root loads increase as rotor radius increases.

Figure 11: Edgewise moment curves along the blade Radius for the four tests. Reference configuration (dashed black line); Design 1 (solid blue line), Design 2 (solid orange line), Design 3 (solid green line).

Figure 12: Flap-wise moment curves along the blade Radius for the four tests. Reference configuration (dashed black line); Design 1 (solid blue line), Design 2 (solid orange line), Design 3 (solid green line).

Table 3: Comparison of edgewise and flap-wise root moments for different rotor designs. The table presents the percentage change ($\Delta\%$) in root moments relative to the reference design for three different designs.

Edgewise moment	root	$\Delta\%$ (x=0)	Flap-wise root moment	$\Delta\%$ (x=0)
Reference		0	Reference	0
Design 1 (R)		1,9	Design 1 (R)	1,5
Design 2 (+5%R)		12,3	Design 2 (+5%R)	13,5
Design 3 (+10%R)		22,2	Design 3 (+10%R)	24,1

3. Baseline floating wind turbine model setup and simulation

The aerodynamic optimization and performance analysis outlined in Section 2.5 provide critical insights into the efficiency and energy capture potential of the redesigned rotor configurations. These results not only validate the benefits of increased rotor radius but also highlight the importance of evaluating the dynamic interactions between the turbine's aerodynamic behaviour and the structural and hydrodynamic forces acting on the floating platform. Building on these findings, the next phase of the study focuses on integrating the optimized rotor designs into a comprehensive simulation framework. This framework captures the coupled dynamics of the turbine and platform system, enabling a detailed assessment of the system's performance under realistic offshore operating conditions. Specifically, the analysis transitions from isolated aerodynamic studies to full-system simulations, incorporating aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, and structural interactions.

The studied turbine is the IEA-15MW UMAINE-SEMI (6) with the UMaine VoltturnUS-S semi-submersible floating platform. This configuration was selected to analyse the system's dynamic behaviour, focusing on the interaction between aerodynamic, hydrodynamic and structural dynamics, while also accounting for the structural flexibility of the blade and tower.

Multiple modules were utilized to capture the key physics governing the system. ElastoDyn (10) modeled the structural dynamics of the blades, tower, and platform, while AeroDyn v15 (2), (9) calculated aerodynamic loads. ServoDyn (11) incorporated control system dynamics, and HydroDyn (12) simulated the hydrodynamic effects on the platform. The mooring system was represented by MoorDyn (13). BeamDyn and SubDyn were excluded to streamline the modeling of blade and substructure dynamics, ensuring computational efficiency while maintaining simulation accuracy.

The turbine degrees of freedom (DOF) were configured to allow realistic dynamic responses. Blade flap-wise and edgewise modes, along with the tower's fore-aft and side-to-side bending modes, were all enabled. Additionally, the platform was permitted to undergo translational motions (surge, sway, heave) and rotational movements (roll, pitch, yaw), ensuring that all relevant dynamics were captured.

The turbine's control system, implemented through the ROSCO.v2.9.0 controller (14), was configured to optimize turbine performance across various operating conditions. The torque control strategy utilized a proportional-integral (PI) controller tuned to maintain an optimal tip-speed ratio (TSR) for maximizing power capture in Region 2. The controller's proportional and integral gains

were specifically calibrated to ensure smooth transitions between operating regions and a maximum variation rate to prevent mechanical overloads. Simultaneously, pitch control was managed through a gain-scheduled PI controller, dynamically adjusting blade pitch angles based on a lookup table of 30 predefined gains corresponding to specific pitch angles. This configuration allowed the turbine to optimize aerodynamic performance and maintain rotor speed stability. Additionally, an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) was employed for real-time wind speed estimation, enhancing the precision of control inputs.

The environmental conditions for the simulation were configured to reflect a typical offshore Mediterranean Sea site. In an initial preliminary analysis aimed at testing the system, three design load cases (DLCs) were considered. These cases involved turbulent wind speeds of 7 m/s, 12 m/s, and 15 m/s generated using TurbSim.v2.00 (15), paired with wave heights of 1 m, 2 m, and 3 m, and corresponding wave periods of 3 s, 4.5 s, and 5.5 s, respectively. These preliminary conditions will later be refined using data derived from the ERA5 database. This refinement will enable the extraction of site-specific DLCs tailored to the Mediterranean context, ensuring more accurate and representative simulation scenarios. TurbSim is a stochastic, full-field wind simulator that generates time-series data representing atmospheric turbulence over a specific domain. In this case, the turbulence is modelled using the “IECKAI” model, corresponding to the Kaimal spectral model defined in the IEC61400 standards for wind turbines; the turbulence intensity is set to IEC turbulence category B, which represents a medium level of turbulence, appropriate for offshore conditions. The grid dimensions, for the reference case, are defined as 21x21, with a grid width and height of 252 meters, sufficient to cover the rotor diameter and hub height of the turbine, and an hub height of 150 meters.

To evaluate the impact of rotor size on performance, three rotor radius configurations were tested: the baseline radius (R_{base}), a 5% increase (R_{05}), and a 10% increase (R_{10}). For each configuration, the twist and chord distributions of the blades were re-optimized to maximize aerodynamic efficiency and the necessary data, the Airfoils and blade data, were obtained from the WP5 analysis. The blade radius was increased from the reference 120.97 m and aerodynamic performance was modelled using the $C_p/C_t/C_q$ table provided for the IEA-15MW turbine. The simulations ran for 1200 s in this preliminary case with a time step of 0.005 s, capturing high-resolution system dynamics. To reflect these changes in rotor size within the wind field simulations, the TurbSim input parameter were adjusted accordingly. Specifically, the grid width and height were scaled proportionally to the increased rotor diameters. The hub height parameter was also updated to reflect the new geometric configuration of the turbine, ensuring consistency with the vertical wind shear profile and turbulence intensity defined in the simulations.

3.2 Automation of DLCs

A Python script was developed to streamline the simulation workflow for multiple Design Load Cases (DLCs). The script automates the generation of wind and wave conditions, initial states, and input files required for OpenFAST simulations. The script enables users to define turbine configurations (e.g., `UMAINE_SEMI_R10`), wind speeds, and hydrodynamic parameters for a variety of load cases. A key feature is the ability to set the number of random seeds, which introduces stochastic variability into the wind cases. This randomization, implemented through user-defined seed counts, ensures the simulation captures a wide range of turbulent wind conditions, increasing the robustness and representativeness of the results. For each seed, the script generates unique turbulent wind fields using TurbSim and dynamically assigns random wave seeds for hydrodynamic conditions in HydroDyn.

Additionally, the script interpolates initial conditions for blade pitch and rotor speed from pre-computed trim results, ensuring accurate starting states for each wind speed scenario. It organizes input files into a structured directory system and automates the generation of necessary input files for TurbSim, InflowWind, and HydroDyn modules. Users can also customize wave heights and periods, which are dynamically assigned for each load case. This level of automation not only simplifies the setup process but also ensures consistency across simulations. The script enables efficient execution of TurbSim and OpenFAST simulations for various DLCs, providing a reliable framework for analysing turbine-platform dynamics and performing parametric studies under realistic offshore conditions.

3.3 Results of the verification tests

This section presents the preliminary results from testing the implemented simulation framework, as outlined in the previous sections. To validate the system, three representative wind speeds—7 m/s, 12 m/s, and 15 m/s—were tested, each using a single random seed to ensure consistent conditions while incorporating stochastic variability. The analysis was conducted for three rotor radius configurations: the baseline radius with optimized twist and chord distributions, as well as configurations with 5% and 10% increases in rotor radius, each with their respective re-optimized aerodynamic parameters. These configurations were chosen to evaluate the impact of rotor size on system dynamics and energy capture. The results provide an initial understanding of the coupled aerodynamic and hydrodynamic behaviour of the 15MW IEA turbine set on the UMaine VoltturnUS-S semi-submersible platform under varying wind conditions. They also establish a foundation for more detailed studies involving additional environmental factors and broader random seed variability.

3.3.3 Average extracted power

Figure 13 compares the average power extracted by the turbine for three different rotor configurations—baseline (RBASE), 5% increased radius (R05), and 10% increased radius (R10)—against the reference turbine (depicted by the continuous blue line). All configurations converge to an average power output of approximately 15 MW at a wind speed of 15 m/s. This convergence is a result of the turbine's speed and pitch control mechanisms, which regulate the rotor speed and blade pitch angles to maintain consistent power output at high wind speeds.

However, notable differences emerge at lower wind speeds, particularly at 7 m/s. Turbines with increased rotor radii exhibited a clear advantage in power extraction. The turbine with a 10% increase in rotor radius (R10) generated significantly more power compared to the baseline and reference configurations. This improvement is due to the increased swept area of the rotor, which allows it to capture more wind energy. This increased efficiency at lower wind speeds effectively lowers the cut-in speed, making the turbine operational and productive under conditions where the baseline configuration might generate less power.

Figure 13: Comparison of the average power extracted by the reference turbine (blue line) and turbines with baseline (RBASE, black line), 5% increased rotor radius (R05, red line), and 10% increased rotor radius (R10, green line) across wind speeds of 7 m/s, 12 m/s

3.3.4 Blade deflection

The plot shown in Figure 14 depicts the blade deflection as a function of wind speed for the reference turbine (dashed black line), the baseline configuration (RBASE, blue line), and turbines with 5% (R05, red line) and 10% (R10, green line) increases in rotor radius. Blade deflection increases with wind speed due to higher aerodynamic loading on the blades, peaking at approximately 12 m/s before decreasing at 15 m/s across all configurations. The reduction at higher wind speeds is a result of pitch control mechanisms, which lower the angle of attack to reduce aerodynamic loads and preserve blade structural integrity.

Turbines with larger rotor radii (R05 and R10) exhibit significantly greater blade deflections at all wind speeds compared to the baseline and reference turbines. This behavior is expected, as larger rotors encounter higher aerodynamic forces from their increased swept area, leading to greater bending moments.

Figure 14: Blade deflection as a function of wind speed for the reference turbine (dashed black line), baseline configuration (RBASE, blue line), and rotors with 5% (R05, red line) and 10% (R10, green line) increased radii.

This plot underscores the importance of considering blade flexibility and structural limits during rotor size optimization, as increased deflection can impact both performance and long-term durability.

3.3.5 Aerodynamic Loads

This subsection examines the distribution of key aerodynamic forces, such as normal and tangential forces, and their translation into structural moments along the blade radius for various rotor configurations, obtained from the wind case of 7 m/s.

The following plots depict the distribution of normal and tangential forces along the blade radius for various rotor configurations: the reference turbine (dashed black line), the baseline configuration (RBASE, blue line), a 5% increase in rotor radius (R05, red line), and a 10% increase in rotor radius (R10, green line).

Figure 15: Distribution of normal force along the blade radius for the reference turbine (dashed black line), baseline configuration (RBASE, blue line), and rotors with 5% (R05, red line) and 10% (R10, green line) increased radii.

Figure 16: Distribution of tangential force along the blade radius for the reference turbine (dashed black line), baseline configuration (RBASE, blue line), and rotors with 5% (R05, red line) and 10% (R10, green line) increased radii.

In the normal force plot (Figure 15), the force increases along the blade radius, peaking before sharply declining near the blade tip. This decrease is attributed to reduced aerodynamic efficiency caused by tip loss effects. The configurations with increased rotor radii (R05 and R10) exhibit higher peaks in normal force compared to the baseline and reference configurations. The R10 configuration, in particular, shows the highest peak, which occurs farther out along the blade due to the extended radius, indicating that larger rotors experience significantly greater aerodynamic loading. This observation emphasizes the trade-off between increased energy capture and the additional structural loads that must be managed in the blade design.

The tangential force distribution (Figure 16) illustrates the aerodynamic driving force responsible for the turbine's rotational motion. Across all configurations, the tangential force increases along the radius, peaking in the mid-span region before tapering off near the tip. The RBASE configuration (blue line) achieves a notably higher tangential force in the optimized mid-span region compared to the reference turbine (dashed black line). This enhancement is directly linked to the blade geometry

optimization, particularly the refined twist and chord distributions, which improve aerodynamic efficiency in this critical area. For the extended rotors (R05 and R10), the tangential force increases along the blade radius and is sustained over a larger portion of the blade compared to the baseline and reference designs. This behavior reflects the advantages of a larger swept area, which allows the extended rotors to capture more wind energy, particularly at lower wind speeds. The ability of the R05 and R10 configurations to maintain a high tangential force across an extended radius underscores the importance of rotor size in improving overall energy capture, especially in moderate wind environments like the Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 17: Edgewise moment distribution along the blade radius for the reference turbine (dashed black line), baseline configuration (RBASE, blue line), and rotors with 5% (R05, red line) and 10% (R10, green line) increased radii.

Figure 18: Flapwise moment distribution along the blade radius for the reference turbine (dashed black line), the baseline configuration (RBASE, blue line), and rotors with 5% (R05, red line) and 10% (R10, green line) increased radii.

In conclusion, the analysis of edgewise and flapwise moments provides valuable insight into the structural implications of the aerodynamic optimizations and increased rotor size. These findings align consistently with the trends observed in the aerodynamic force distributions (Figure 17 and Figure

18), reinforcing the interplay between aerodynamic performance and structural loading. Furthermore, even when introducing additional complexities into the simulation, such as hydrodynamic forces, blade elasticity, and turbulent wind, the results remain consistent with the initial aerodynamic analysis conducted on the rotor. The extended rotors (R05 and R10), with their larger swept areas, continue to demonstrate an ability to capture more energy, as reflected in the increased moments along the blade span. This highlights the importance of balancing structural considerations with aerodynamic enhancements when optimizing rotor size, ensuring that performance gains are achieved without compromising system stability under realistic offshore operating conditions.

4. Conclusions

This report details the aerodynamic optimization of a 15 MW offshore wind turbine blade using a framework that integrates surrogate modeling, blade element momentum theory, and genetic algorithms. The primary objective of the optimization was to maximize the Annual Energy Production (AEP) by adjusting the blade's twist and chord distributions, tailored to the moderate wind conditions typical of the Mediterranean Sea. The approach effectively enhanced aerodynamic performance across three design configurations compared to the state-of-the-art open-source reference wind turbine for offshore applications: the baseline rotor (Design 1), a rotor with a 5% increase in radius (Design 2), and a rotor with a 10% increase in radius (Design 3).

Design 3 achieved the highest AEP improvement, with a 20.6% increase compared to the reference design. This improvement is directly linked to the enhanced energy capture enabled by the larger rotor area, demonstrating the benefits of increased rotor size for offshore wind turbines in moderate wind environments. However, increasing the rotor radius also resulted in higher root loads, with the edgewise and flap-wise root moments showing maximum percentage increases of 24% and 22%, respectively, for Design 3.

The document also reports on the implementation of the simulation framework to analyze the dynamic behavior of the 15 MW rotors obtained in the optimization phase. The turbines were modeled on the UMaine VoltturnUS-S semi-submersible platform to simulate the entire assembly of a floating offshore wind turbine. The simulation methodology incorporated OpenFAST modules to model aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, and structural interactions, explicitly considering structural flexibility for the blades and tower. A Python-based automatic Design Load Cases generation and post-processing interface was used, enabling efficient execution of TurbSim and OpenFAST simulations while ensuring consistency across varying configurations and environmental conditions. The virtual turbine models achieved their rated power of 15 MW across all rotor configurations, demonstrating the ability of the ROSCO controller to regulate rotor speed and pitch angles effectively to achieve average turbine responses aligned with expected performance. Variations in rotor radius revealed clear trade-offs: larger rotors (with 5% and 10% increases) enhanced energy capture at lower wind speeds, including in floating and turbulent wind conditions. However, the increased size introduced higher structural loads, as evidenced by elevated normal and tangential forces and higher blade moments.

As outcome, this report also describes the baseline floating wind turbine models from which the consortium can set the new tailored design practices for Mediterranean Sea applications pointing to further improve the wind turbine performance while significantly reducing the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) associated with the final concept.

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